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2716_Upper Sorbian

Ethnologue:

- A language of Germany
- ISO/DIS 639-3: hsb
- Population: 15,000 (1996). Ethnic population: 70,000 to 110,000 with Lower Sorbian (1999 Ken Sasahara).
- Region: Upper Saxony, eastern Germany, principal towns Bautzen (Budysin, Catholic) and Kamenz (Protestant). Perhaps a few in Texas, USA.
- Alternate names: Obersorbisch, Haut Sorabe, Upper Lusatian, Wendish, Hornjoserbski, Hornoserbski
- Dialects: Bautzen, Kamenz.
- Classification: Indo-European, Slavic, West, Sorbian
- Language use: Zgusta (1974) says Upper Sorbian and Lower Sorbian are two standard languages. Use of Sorbian is authorized in local government and schools. Increasing literature production. Now accepted as a minority language. 40,000 to 45,000 others have some knowledge of it. Most speakers are older adults. Most of the monolinguals are the very young (Stephens 1976). Nearly all also use German.
- Language development: Taught in primary schools. Newspapers. Radio programs. TV. Bible: 1728–1797.

Source: H. Schuster-Šewc: Grammar of the Upper Sorbian Language
LINCOS Studies in Slavic Linguistics 03
1996 LINCOS EUROPA, München – Newcastle

contact language: German (especially Upper Saxon), Lower Sorbian

I. _____ Phonotactics

initially:

- *rʒ; *wʃ
- /h/ is only pronounced at the beginning of a word preceding a vowel or intervocalically; in all other positions it is not pronounced (orthographically it exists, whether it exists also underlying, the grammar does not tell) except [bahno] 'swamp'
 - in dialects /h/ is often substituted for [j] before front vowels
ex.: /nɔ̃hi/ > [nɔ̃ji] 'feet, legs'
 - before /u, ɔ, a/ often realized as [w]
ex.: /nɔ̃ha/ > [nɔ̃wa] 'foot, leg'
- /x/ > [kʰ] if it is morpheme initially - e.g. can also occur word initially, e.g. no [x] in word initial position - therefore [kʰ] occurs stem initial if it is preceded by a prefix; [kʰ]

also occurs if it follows /t/ and in derivatives of the morphemes -xɔd, -xad, -xaw;

ex.: k^hleb 'bread'
tk^ha 'flee'

medially:

- /a/ with very few exceptions (certain case number suffixes) does not occur between two palatals or palatalized consonants: allophone [ɛ]
- [e], [o] only occur in stressed syllables; otherwise [ɛ], [ɔ]
- /s^j/ only occurs after /t/

Clusters:

- the combination of consonants into consonant clusters is governed by certain rules:
 - obstruent+sonorant as onset is permitted, but sonorant+obstruent is not allowed

Syllable:

- No rules cited
- Observed in examples:
 - CV: wɔ.da 'water'
 - CCV: stɔ.pa 'sole'; bro.da 'beard, chin'; ʃmi.tsa 'plant-louse'
 - CCVC: knɔt 'mole'; ʃrub 'screw'
 - CVC: pɔs 'dog'; kor.bik 'little basket'
 - CCCC: pstru.ha 'trout'
 - CVCCC: pɔrst 'finger'
- a word can consist of up to five syllables
- a syllable may consist of a vowel only (glottal plosive is not discussed)

II. Phonological Rules

- /n/ > [ŋ] / _ Velars
- cluster simplification: /t, d/ > ø / _n
- /w, j, ɸ/ tend to elide before a consonant
 - these sounds also have the tendency to be replaced by one another
- loss of initial /j/ results in a unique stem alternation in the word [stwa] 'parlour, room'
 - after prepositions this word shows the initial /j/, ex. wɛ jstwe 'in the parlour'
 - (alternative proposal: insertion of /j/ at the beginning of /stwa/ if it is preceded by a preposition)
- Palatalization: nasals and plosives; among the affricates only /ts/; fricatives but not /s, ʃ, ʒ, j/; Liquids

- Palatalized consonants can be either distinctive or non-distinctive, e.g. allophones

- Palatalized allophones occur before /i/: f^j, v^j, t^j, d^j, s^j, l^j, k^j, g^j, x^j, h^j

- Depalatalization:

- Many of the formerly palatalized phonemes (see palatalization) are subject to depalatalization in certain positions, most often in clusters where the consonant following an originally palatalized consonant is non-palatalized or in word-final position

- where an epenthetic [j] is inserted before a palatalized segment and after /ɛ/, the consonant preceding /ɛ/ depalatalizes but only if that consonant is the palatalized member of a palatalization opposition, i.e. not an inherently palatalized segment

Ex.: /pʲɛnk/ > [pɛjnk] 'tree-stump' (but /n/ in the example is not indicated as being palatalized)

- Voicing Assimilation: a voiced consonant becomes voiceless preceding a voiceless consonant or a voiceless consonant becomes voiced preceding a voiced consonant either within words and between words

- Not further described when does the devoicing and when does the voicing happen

- Voicing assimilation does not always take place, where it theoretically could occur

Ex. – within words:

/litʲba/ > [lidʒba] 'number, quantity'
/susɔdka/ > [susɔtka] '(woman) neighbor'

Ex. – between words:

/mex ʒita/ > [mexʒita] 'sack of grain / rye'

- Final Devoicing: ex.: /noʒ/ > [noʃ] 'knife'

- Centralization of /i/ : /i/ becomes more centralized (~ [i]) but not fully centralized after non-palatalized consonants

- this slightly centralized vowel changes to [ɔ] after labials in unstressed position, otherwise it surfaces in unstressed position as [ɛ]

- in colloquial speech: /w/ > [ɦ] / #_u; ex.: wutɔra > futɔra 'Tuesday'

- tendency – insertion of non-phonemic [j] before palatalized consonants and after /ɛ/

- Alternations in inflectional and derivational morphology which occur mainly at the morpheme boundary, i.e. root-final consonants alternate in a position before desinences or word-formation suffixes:

i. Stem final velar alternations in word formation and the vocative:

k ~ tʃ, h ~ ʒ, x ~ ʃ

Ex.: /brjof/ 'bank, embarkement' > [brjoʒ-k] DIM

ii. C ~ Cʲ :

- this stem final consonant alternation is conditioned by particular morphological categories, i.e. the endings /-e/, /-a/ and /-i/; but the alternant is not always the palatalized counterpart, but: t~tʃ; d~dʒ; w~lʲ; r~ʃ; k~tʂ; h~z; x~ʃ (this alternation seems to be triggered by /-e/ and /-i/ only)

Ex.: /padux/ 'thief' > [padufʲ] NOM.PL.MASC.ANIM

iii. Ø ~ V (where V=e, o, the more centralized /i/)

- Occurs in stem-final syllables of a larger number of words, with the NOM/ ACC.SG.MASC showing the vowel, but none of the oblique cases do

- There seems to be phonetic conditioning at work since the stem vowel is there in word-final position, but is absent in non-final position, i.e. when a vowel initial suffix follows the stem

Ex.: dʒen 'day' NOM.ACC.SG.MASC > dnja GEN

- Occurs also on the present tense of certain verbs but without the phonetic conditioning above, i.e. the alternant stem forms are both found in a position before a vowel

Ex.: ʒɛr-u 'eat (of an animal)' 1.SG.PRES > ʒra-tʃ INF

In some disyllabic words, the alternation is optional

iv. Qualitative change of vowels:

in certain masculine substantives the vowels /e/, /o/ and /a/ of the NOM.SG change to [ɛ], [ɔ] in other case forms

Ex.: /woz/ 'wagon.NOM.SG' > [wɔza] 'wagon.GEN.SG'

- In feminine substantives with the root vowel /a/, this /a/ changes to /e/ between palatalized consonants in the dative and locative singular and in the nominative and accusative dual

v. monosyllabic substantives exhibit [e] instead of [ɛ] in DAT.SG, LOC.SG and NOM/ ACC.DU

ex.: po jstwe 'around / about the room'

vi. insertion [w] between the stem and the past transgressive suffix /-ʃi/ if the stem ends in a vowel

ex.: [wuwizdawʃi] 'having booed, after booing'

[spletʃi] 'having woven, after weaving'

III. Stress

- Vowel length is not distinctive, only a matter of emphasis; stressed vowels are lengthened

- normally on the first syllable of a word
- in speech stream it marks the beginning of a word
- in words of more than three syllables the primary accent occurs on the first syllable and a secondary one on the penultimate
- in the case of compounds the secondary accent falls on the first syllable of the second member of the compound:

ex.: ['knifi,wjazar] 'book binder'

- superlatives of adjectives and adverbs prefixed with naj- also have a secondary accent

ex.: ['naj,spefnifi] 'the fastest'

- if stronger emphasis is placed on the basic stem, the order of stress can change, so that the primary accent is in the basic stem and the secondary accent on the prefix

ex.: [,naj'spefnifi] 'the fastest'

- special rules for the accentuation of prepositions:

- a preposition that contains a vowel always takes the accent if it occurs before a mono- or disyllabic word

ex.: 'kɛ mʃi 'to church'; 'wotɛ mʃɛ 'from church'

- the complement of the preposition attracts the accent if emphasis is put on it, the preposition in this case does not receive stress

- if some attributes stand between the preposition and its complement noun, stress is assigned to the attribute

- complement noun of the preposition usually retain its stress if it comprises more than two syllables

- loan words preserve in general their original accent

- words ending in -ita, -ija, -ɔwatʃ, -erɔwatʃ have stress on the antepenultimate

ex.: aw'tɔrita 'authority'; tɛlɛ'fɔnɔwatʃ 'to telephone'

- in the colloquial language and in the dialects reduction or elimination of unstressed vowels occur

ex.: ɦɔtɔwarnitʃa > ɦɔtɔwarnʃa 'wardrobe assistant'

- sentence stress falls on the last word of the unit, but it can shift according to emphasis

V. Clitics

- Proclitics: unstressed prepositions (see stress rules for prepositions)
- Enclitics: never stressed, attach to a preceding word forming with it a rhythmic unit
 - Pronouns, monosyllabic conjunctions, monosyllabic particles, forms of the auxiliary verb /bitʃ/ 'to be'